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Introduction

Despite the ongoing war in Ukraine, the Kyiv School of Economics (KSE) is considered as a premier, resilient educational and research ecosystem in Ukraine that is currently undergoing rapid growth and structural changes. One of them is the introduction of systemic support to KSE researchers in international cooperation and grant project activity, facilitated by the new structural unit - **International Project Office (IPO)**, established under WP4 of the BRIDGE Project.

The IPO at KSE oversees the broad scope of international projects and programmes, supporting and developing research, educational, social outreach, student and faculty mobility initiatives. The Office operation embraces two main project life-cycles: (1) project design (grant writing) at the pre-award phase and (2) project management at the post-award phase. It is aimed to serve as the university hub for fostering innovative ideas and their transformation into projects, building capacity to work in a cooperative environment and project-based culture, accumulation and sharing of good practices, maintaining and development of networks with the main stakeholders.

The KSE International Project Office is established at institutional level as the structural unit of the International Cooperation Department, aimed at professional services to KSE departments, research and educational centers and individual researchers.

International Project Office mission

The **mission** of the International Project Office is a systemic facilitation of the global integration and impactful development of the KSE research and academic community through collaboration within international research and educational programmes.

Long-term strategic objectives

IPO strategic objectives determine the core guiding components of international project activity and are aligned with institutional long-term priorities:

- **Integration and Networks:** driving the University's global presence by fostering membership in international partnerships, alliances and consortia, as well as collaborations with public and private sectors, NGOs and local communities.
- **Added Value and Resources:** attraction and meaningful utilization of intellectual, financial, material and technological resources to address the challenges and facilitate sustainable development.
- **Quality and Integrity:** continuous enhancement of the quality of academic and research services and products, cultivating the culture of quality and integrity in all operations, coherence and alignment with international standards and cross-cutting values.
- **Visibility and Impact:** promotion of the University brand, expertise and impact, formation of centers of excellence, knowledge transfer and broad communication.
- **Capacity Building:** support and development of research groups, individual researchers and young talents to work internationally in a project-based environment, to design and

manage projects, and institutionally to provide for necessary policies, structures and services for international project activity.

Short-term goals and implementation tasks

In the short-term perspective (1-2 years) the KSE IPO will target the following goals supported by implementation tasks:

- **Establishment of the international project environment:**
 - launching efficient communication and information channels for KSE researchers in internal corporate messengers and systems;
 - design of accessible databases of grant opportunities, partnership network, on-going projects, supporting resources;
 - organisation of regular meetings, programme presentations, information days, project ideas workshops, best practice sharing events;
 - delivery of regular consultations and support related to project application process and project management.
- **Design of policies and business processes for project writing and management:**
 - development of institutional policies and procedures with determination of necessary institutional rules, criteria and rates;
 - development and approval of internal business processes with functional engagement of necessary University units, including IPO, International Cooperation Department, Financial and Legal offices, supply, event and communication units;
 - introduction of related workflow and document circulation models with clear distribution of roles and responsibilities.
- **Building an expert community for international project activities:**
 - raising the cohort of grant writers and project managers at all University departments;
 - organization of special training sessions for University researchers and administrators devoted to grant writing and grant project management based on EU best practices and experience;
 - introduction of the peer-review practices for better quality of projects.
- **Increasing the quantity and quality of international projects with KSE participation:**
 - engagement with national offices of the main grant programmes in the area of higher education and research, in particular EU Horizon Europe and Erasmus+ programmes;
 - organisation of the complex campaigns to facilitate project design in frames of the targeted programmes: learning about opportunities - shaping ideas - building partnerships - preparing projects with continuous mentoring and peer support.

Key Performance Indicators

The **Key Performance Indicators** (KPIs) for the International Project Office have been defined, while their values will be revised and agreed on the annual basis. For 2026 IPO KPIs are the following:

- Number of grant applications submitted per year - no less than 50.
- Number of grant programmes targeted (diversification) - no less than 10.
- Amount of grant funding attracted - 500 000 Euro.
- Percentage of successful grant applications - no less than 10%.
- Number of University departments involved - all 5.
- Number of trained (consulted) researchers and project managers - no less than 100.

ANNEX 1 – International Project Office structure and staff profiles

Two project managers and two grant advisors are in direct subordination to the Head of the International Project Office. Additionally, the cohort of project managers are appointed at the level of Departments.

Grant Advisor profile

For the grant advisor position we expect a professional responsible for guiding researchers, faculty, and academic staff through the entire lifecycle of securing external funding for research, educational projects, or development initiatives. He/she acts as intermediaries between academic staff and funding bodies, helping to turn project ideas into competitive, compliant, and fundable proposals.

Key responsibilities include:

- ❖ Assisting with the structuring, writing, editing, and formatting of grant applications, particularly for complex, interdisciplinary, or international projects.
- ❖ Monitoring and promoting relevant national, EU, and private funding schemes that align with institutional and faculty strategies.

- ❖ Offering expertise on funder requirements, regulations, and proposal guidelines to ensure compliance.
- ❖ Collaborating with financial managers to prepare project budgets and financial justifications.
- ❖ Organizing workshops and seminars to keep researchers updated on funding opportunities and best practices in grant writing.
- ❖ Assisting in identifying the right partners and consortia for large-scale grant applications.

Qualification

Education: University degree (Master or PhD).

Expertise:

- Deep knowledge of the grant lifecycle (pre-award and post-award), including budget development and project management
- Proven track-record in leading or consulting on funding proposals is a plus
- Knowledge of the organization of research and development activities in Ukraine and the European Union.

Communication: Exceptional writing and editing skills are essential for translating complex scientific or educational ideas into compelling narratives for reviewers.

Interpersonal skills: Ability to work in "matrix" teams, collaborating with diverse stakeholders across academic and administrative units.

Personal qualities:

- Attention to detail
- Flexibility, effective time management skills, and ability to meet deadlines
- Strong communication skills
- A good team player
- Well-developed analytical skills
- Ability to quickly learn and adapt to changes

Project Manager profile

For the project manager we engaged professionals responsible for leading, implementing, and reporting on educational projects funded by international programs (e.g., EU/Erasmus+, USAID, UNESCO, UNICEF). His/her role bridges strategic goals with field-level execution, requiring expertise in both project management and donor compliance.

Key responsibilities include:

- ❖ Overseeing projects from inception to closure, including designing workplans, managing budgets, and implementing activities.
- ❖ Ensuring strict adherence to donor regulations (narrative and financial) to avoid audit issues, often managing complex reporting requirements.

- ❖ Providing smooth interaction between University Departments involved into the project fulfilment.
- ❖ Managing relationships with project partners, local partners, government bodies (e.g., Ministries of Education), and other institutions to ensure smooth collaboration.
- ❖ Tracking project progress against indicators, conducting assessments, and reporting on project impact.
- ❖ Managing project funds, ensuring cost-effectiveness, and developing financial revisions when necessary.

Qualification

Education: University degree (Master or PhD).

Expertise:

- Proficiency in project management tools and methodologies
- Excellent written/spoken English is essential, along with the ability to navigate multicultural teams and local contexts
- Understanding of educational systems, research procedures and curriculum development
- High-level adaptability to manage risks, tight deadlines, and complex, sometimes volatile environments
- Proficiency in Microsoft Office (Excel, Word) and collaboration tools (Teams, Zoom, Asana)
- Overseeing phased budgets, procurement plans, and monitoring financial deviations to prevent fund misuse.

Cultural Intelligence: High adaptability for working in multicultural environments and volatile or complex settings.

Personal qualities:

- Attention to detail
- Flexibility, effective time management skills, and ability to meet deadlines
- Strong communication skills
- A good team player
- Well-developed analytical skills
- Ability to quickly learn and adapt to changes

ANNEX 2 – International Project Office services and activities

Grant writing and application submission:

- Monitoring current international grant programs (Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, BMBF, NSF, etc.), open Calls offering grant funds for research, education and infrastructure projects.
- Providing assistance in writing competitive applications in accordance with the requirements of international donor programs.
- Helping structure the proposal and construct the budget.
- Gathering documents and submitting in the participant portal (or another submission system).
- Contributing to writing some sections of proposal (e.g. parts like management or impact and dissemination).
- Advising researchers on how consortiums should be constructed.
- Proofreading of written project applications providing further recommendations.
- Organizing consortia meetings and managing partner communication.
- Collection of project ideas of research teams.
- Maintaining databases of programmes, partnership networks and relevant resources.

Project management and monitoring:

- Helping with Grant Agreement negotiations if funded.
- Monitoring grant requirements and obligations.
- Giving information on project implementation procedure in general and in each particular case due to the donor's rules.
- Establishing interaction between University departments and project implementers.
- Providing financial management assistance.
- Conducting various communication activities, such as building a website, popularization.
- Maintaining project documentation.
- Monitoring the implementation of project activities according to the prescribed schedule, if needed.
- Carrying out internal audit and monitoring compliance with donor's requirements.
- Preparing reports.

Development of international partnerships:

- Establishing cooperation with universities, research centers and companies.
- Organizing joint research initiatives.
- Preparing memorandums and cooperation agreements.

Enhancing competences in grant writing and project management:

- Organizing and participating in seminars/information days held by international donors, funds, programs on the procedure for providing and implementing educational, infrastructure and investment projects.
- Conducting focused training for University teachers and researchers related to international project management and grant writing.
- Designing guidelines and instructions on grant project application and fulfilment processes.